

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Innovation Ecosystems activity final report Deliverable 1.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides an analysis of the performance and evolution of the Innovation Ecosystems in project TransformAr, that is, the regional structures set up to support adequate conditions for the co-creation of solutions.

Deliverable 1.3 can be useful as a stand-alone, for the theory and methods behind this deliverable can be replicated in participatory processes and continuous engaging of stakeholders, regardless of discipline or socio-economic context.

It is recommended, though, to go through it in the company of the previous reports from this Work Package 1, and to contextualise the lengthier accounts of co-creation exchanges held and documented in Work Package 3.

In terms of structure, it is divided in three parts, and it reads both ways. The first block covers the (1) implementation of the Multi-Actor Approach defined early in the project, in a chronological fashion; the second part outlines the (2) results from monitoring and their validation from the partners; and the last segment deals with an (3) extended theoretical framework that allows for an in depth analysis, and that can be replicated in the future so that other transformative agents can kick start and navigate stakeholder engagement.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CC – Climate Change

DF – Demo Facilitators

EU – European Union

IE – Innovation Ecosystem

II – Interactive Innovation

IIB – Interactive Innovation Broker

FT – Follower Territories

KCS – Key Community Systems

LD – Lighthouse Demonstrators

MAA – Multi-Actor Approach

RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation

SAB – Stakeholders' Advisory Board

TA – Transformational Adaptation

TAB – Transformational Adaptation Block

TSP – Technical Support Partner

WP – Work Package

WPL – Work Package Leader

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1.0 IMPLEMENTATION

In this first chapter, a context for the actions is provided to understand the evolution of the methods implemented and data generated. The Multi-Actor Approach was implemented to bridge research and practice, create adequate conditions for quick and widespread adoption, and ensure the continuity of the knowledge transfer beyond project lifetime. For a detailed description of the methodology for Multi-Actor Approach, and the requirements of co-creation in Transformational Adaptation (TA), please refer to Deliverable 1.1. A list of the socio-economic context of the Key Community Systems and the Key Stakeholders is available in Deliverable 1.2. A description of the co-creation activities for Adaptation Pathways and Action Plans development can be found in Deliverables 3.3, 3.8 and 3.9.

1.1 Strategy

The first Specific Objective of TransformAr was to demonstrate the potential of co-innovation processes for Transformational Adaptation (TA) towards climate resilience in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. This was done with the assistance of 6 Lighthouse Demonstrators (demos, further on) and a Follower Territory (FT). In short, these regional networks are at the centre of each Innovation Ecosystem, meant to creating a shared ownership of solutions and increasing joint decision-making towards systemic change [1].

To ensure the participation and active engagement of TransformAr cross-sectoral and multi-scale stakeholders from the local and regional communities, a methodology for co-innovation alongside multiple actors was put into place based on a Multi-Actor Approach and the values defined by EIP-AGRI [2].

Figure 1. Multi-Actor Approach values as defined by EIP-AGRI.

The governance model for the Innovation Ecosystems, in accordance to MAA values, was conceived as a matrix organizational structure with geographical and technical dimensions to address the necessary balance between regional and technical requirements. Detailed rules for the governance and decision making were set as well as operational management procedures in a non-iterative feedback cycle. Additionally, the figure of the Broker [2] was created to assist in the implementation of the methodology and help evaluate the performance of the different demos.

1.2 Matrix and first consultations

The Matrix (D1.2) compiles a list of Key Stakeholders, the co-builders from a bottom-up perspective. They are representative actors from their Key Community Systems, able to generate knowledge and motivated to play a strategic role in accelerating Transformational Adaptation to Climate Change. Demo Duos were tasked with identifying and verifying their effective role and influence within each Demonstrator. Key Stakeholders often possess previous tidings with the local partners which reinforces their trust and commitment with TransformAr.

Arranged into seven groups, the Key Stakeholders conformed the core of the co-creation activities. It must be stated that the Matrix was conceived, from the start, to be updated as the project carried on and the community building rendered evermore involved local actors. This was true specially for the Bankability reports, which featured stakeholders with a growing role. Some considerations on the limits of the Matrix can be found in the last part of this document.

At the same time, a initial row consultation workshops was considered to help build a shared vision of the Adaptation Pathways. In the interest of time and practicality, the initial consultations were rearranged and finally replaced with information collected on pre-planned surveys within T3.1.1. The combined push of the Matrix and the early Multi-Actor Approach methodology was, regardless, pivotal to the design and outcomes of the initial Adaptation Pathways workshops.

From February 2022 to January 2023, the six demonstrators of the TransformAr project (West Country Region (UK), Oristano (Italy), Egaleo (Greece), City of Lappeenranta (Finland), Guadeloupe (France), Galicia (Spain) organised workshops to apply the methodology to co-create Adaptation Pathways at both territorial and sectoral levels.

In parallel, improvements to the methodology were compiled in a publication, presented in November 2022 at the ICERI Conference, titled 'Interactive Innovation Broker: a consensual framework for Multi-Actor Approach practical implementation'. In it FEUGA stressed the importance of continuity, creating and maintaining conditions of balance and access to knowledge so as to ensure the viability of the solutions and restore the Innovation Ecosystems once the project came to an end [2].

1.3 Best Practices

Work Package 1 was responsible for 6 Best Practices sessions. Starting in mid-2023, these were structured exchanges where project partners and stakeholders share experiences, methods, and lessons learned to highlight what works in practice and how it can be applied elsewhere. Its importance for the stakeholder

engagement assessment can be understood from two perspectives: that of horizontal integration of knowledge, and that of the two-way, vertical feedback. Crucially, these sessions contributed to make tacit into evident knowledge that otherwise would have taken much effort to bring to light, and made partners learn faster and to greater effect based on relatable experiences.

The regular exchange of experiences and best practices among the various demonstrator teams and other stakeholders made partners act proactively in addressing common challenges and avoiding potential implementation hurdles. Each session focused on a specific topic crucial to the project's success; hence covered a range of subjects, from stakeholder management and change management to technical topics like making data available and accessible. This structured approach ensured that the discussions were targeted and productive [3].

After the sessions, VERHAERT compiled the insights and 'tips & tricks' into three thematic best practice reports; each synthesised the learnings from two sessions. Designated as D1.5 (stakeholder management & change management), D1.6 (How to make data available and accessible & developing transformational pathways), and D1.7 (A multi-actor approach to governance & looking back on TransformAr and transformational adaptation), serve as a permanent record of the key takeaways. Additionally, the final reports were later published online with valuable 'learning stories', making the knowledge accessible to a wider audience both within and outside the project. This entire process was a collaborative effort, with VERHAERT coordinating the sessions and all demonstrators, technical partners, and the Municipality of Gjovik actively contributing.

BEST PRACTICES: Stakeholder Management

Stakeholder management plays a critical role in ensuring project success by effectively addressing the needs and expectations of key stakeholders. It involves identifying and prioritizing these stakeholders, understanding their requirements, and actively engaging with them throughout the project lifecycle. By doing so, project managers can foster positive relationships, gain valuable insights, and adapt to changes that may arise. This active involvement not only enhances project communication but also enables project teams to adjust their strategies and plans accordingly, resulting in improved project outcomes.

Steps:

- 1 IDENTIFICATION**
Identifying stakeholders is a vital step in project management. It involves recognizing the individuals or groups who are relevant to the project and have a vested interest in its success or may be affected by it.
- 2 ANALYSIS**
Stakeholder analysis plays a crucial role in project management by providing valuable insights into stakeholders' interests, concerns, and priorities.
- 3 PLAN**
Stakeholder planning is a critical step in project management that focuses on addressing the needs, expectations, concerns, and issues of stakeholders in a strategic manner.
- 4 ENGAGEMENT**
Stakeholder engagement is a crucial aspect of project management that emphasizes active involvement of stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle.

Key Tips for Effective Stakeholders Management

Do's:

- Identify all stakeholders
- Analyze stakeholders needs, influence and interest
- Develop a communication plan
- Engage stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle
- Address stakeholder concerns/issues
- Manage stakeholder relationships
- Build Trust

Don'ts:

- Ignore stakeholders needs and expectations
- Overpromise and underdeliver
- Exclude stakeholders
- Disregard feedback
- Make assumptions
- React only when there is a problem

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Figure 2. Best Practices first report excerpt as an online learning story.

Figure 2. Best Practices first report excerpt as an online learning story.

Ultimately, the Best Practices sessions provided direct feedback that otherwise would have been difficult to find, codify and validate in the creation of this D1.3. Besides, they keep record of valuable experiments that hardly have a place for in other Deliverables or results, such as the Scenario Exploration or Systems Thinking, practices that should receive further support for they can counter the innovation inertia at regional and local level, enabling transformative change in the form of alternative partnerships and more radical solutions. This is further explored in the next chapter.

1.4 Climate perception and Action Plans

WP1 also played a part in assessing stakeholders' attitudes and beliefs that hinder or facilitate the adoption of the behaviours leading to transformative change. Ultimately, three outcomes were produced by USC: a novel coding system, a protocol for Focus Group implementation, and a report with the analysis of the implications of attitudes and beliefs towards the solutions and the alignment of the findings with future project phases and beyond project lifetime. These are featured in D1.4 Beliefs towards transformational adaptation conceptual map.

The research group COSOYPA thus provided the groundwork to analyse social acceptance and a resource to support subsequent project phases. Additionally, the qualitative analysis carried out used an inductive coding system, structured around seven semantic domains, providing insights into barriers and facilitators across the different regional contexts, further enriching the understanding of stakeholders' attitudes, and complementing and supporting the Discrete Choice Experiment later carried out in TransformAr.

This information came at a time when the demonstrators were wrapping up the definition of the Adaptational Pathways and translating them into Action Plans for the solution implementation and governance. From January 2024 to July 2024, demonstrators conducted internal works and collaborative workshops to refine their adaptation pathways, select the preferred pathways and develop the adaptation action plans. Notably, a methodological toolkit was provided by ACTIERRA, complementing the Playbook (D3.10) to support the demonstrators, step by step, in co-creating and realising the action plans (see the Toolkit for adaptive action planning in Deliverable D3.7).

1.5 Other sources of feedback

Due to the expected launch of an EU-level Community of Practice in January 2023, sponsored by the Mission Adaptation and later the Mission Adaptation Implementation Platform, or MIP4Adapt, it was proposed that WP1 and WP7 unite forces in creating a Network on Climate Change Adaptation (NCCA), so that TransformAr and its sister projects could contribute to the Mission's own Community of Practice via working groups with representatives from WP1 and WP6. WP7, which later overtook the coordination of the Network, was also responsible for webinars and other joint events WP7.

MIP4Adapt launched the technical assistance and working groups in July 2023, and thus WP1 integrated the corresponding Stakeholder Engagement Working Group. FEUGA was later designated co-champion of that Group, accompanying project AGORA in collating a set of recommendations and methodologies from 180 participants from the Horizon Europe framework. The conclusions, a complement to the DIY Manual for stakeholder engagement, were presented in May 2025 during the event ‘Enhancing Adaptation Actions: Outputs from Thematic Working Groups’.

Previously, works had already started in collaboration with the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN), a global initiative for the United Nations, to present TransformAr’s strategy for co-creation of solutions. The Network first shared preliminary findings in July 2023 for the SDSN Climate Hub, during the online round table ‘Developing systemic solutions for climate adaptation and mitigation through Multi-Stakeholder Approaches’, featuring sister projects ARSINOE and IMPETUS as well. Another opportunity presented itself the year after, with the presentation of the Galicia demonstrator among the relevant cases of climate change adaptation in Spain.

2024 was also the year that the European Environment Agency launched the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) on the Mission Portal [4]. Designed for local and regional authorities planning and implementing adaptational plans and actions, this guide influenced the review of the procedures, tools and priorities originally defined in Deliverable 1.1.

The Network also contributed to a policy brief Stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation & resilience: Learnings from EU Mission on Adaptation projects, published in July 2024 via the Horizon Results Booster [5].

1.6 Index and monthly meetings

Considering the challenges ahead, WP1 worked in combining the latest development of the theoretical framework with feedback from the First Review Meeting, the Executive Committee, partners taking part in the change management best practices sessions, and the discussions held in the context of the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN). As a result, a first draft of the Interactive Innovation Index, a tool for decision-making, resource allocation and self-assessment in project afterlife, was presented and discussed with the partners during a second consensus meeting in December 2023.

During the sixth Consortium Meeting, however, the partners agreed to postpone the introduction of the Interactive Innovation Index tool in favour of streamlining the most urgent stakeholder-related activities. The tool was meant to aid the Demo Duos in reflecting on, and also comparing visually, the status of their own Innovation Ecosystem from the perspectives of internal balance, capacity development, coalition-building, and the role of facilitators. The Index can be further explored in Deliverable 1.7.

Figure 3. Interactive Innovation Index as a visual representation of different demos.
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As a more direct alternative, monthly meetings with demonstrators started in May 2024 to address pressing issues and keep a project perspective when it mattered most. They provided a steady inflow of information, vital for the accuracy and therefore the usefulness of the continuous monitoring system. More on this in the second part, Results.

1.7 Final consultations

The second planned row of Consultation Workshops were the last mandatory in-person activity involving stakeholders. They took the form of a themed bundle of the remaining WP1, WP5 and WP6 workshops for collecting information on the solutions implemented and identify how and which actors will continue working beyond TransformAr, a complement to the conclusions shared in WP3.

Based on the experience of the Galicia demonstrator, the Consultation workshops were refined, and a template was distributed to assist the local partners and obtain feedback beforehand. Its modularity made possible switching parts depending on the information still pending and the availability of stakeholders, pointing to the researchers that could provide assistance, and where to find the materials necessary to carry out the activity.

2.0 RESULTS

This chapter is dedicated to the results of the continuous monitoring. A set of control parameters were defined at the start of the activities involving local communities, to be updated based on the report templates provided to the Demo Facilitators. However, to avoid duplicities, the accountability was instead diverted to the full, detailed reports from Work Package 3.

A crucial step from the procedures, the self-assessment by the Demo Duos, had to be generated separately; but the chosen tool, the Index, was deemed too complex to be implemented just as the local partners were dealing with the Action Plans, the implementation of solutions and the reporting on the Key Performance Indicators. An alternative was then devised for the near end of TransformAr; more on this in Part 3, Extended Framework.

Regardless, the continuous monitoring offered great value when spotting trends and looking at inconsistencies, whether at local level or between demonstrators. It also helped understand the different approaches to workshop structure and follow up, so linking activities and planning for the future became easier just as the project was exhausting the resources allocated to the partners responsible for engagement, with stakeholders potentially facing an unbearable pace and thus risking the viability of the late activities. On the other hand, the control parameters allowed to take advantage of the demonstrator momentum whenever possible.

During 2024, Galicia was able to lead the last consultation row based on this data. The same can be said about the distribution of Open Days. Consequently, the themed workshops of the last year must be attributed to this ability to plan ahead, merging the second part of the Bankability Reports, the Market Validation and the Ownership of Solutions with the remaining consultations.

The monitoring tool had proven enough to coordinate, raise the efficiency and provide results in time for the different tasks, while avoiding stakeholder disenfranchisement. TransformAr carried out 45 major activities involving local actors with well over 250 participants belonging to the key stakeholder category as established in D1.1 and D1.2. This included WP1 consultations, WP3 pathways and action plans definition, WP4 nudging and learning stories, the start of WP5 bankability interviews, WP6 Discrete Choice Experiment and market validation planning, WP7 Open Days and two webinars from the NCCA, plus the citizen science programme deployed by WRT from Month 9 onwards.

2.1 Control parameters

Defined following the completion of Deliverable 1.1., the Control Parameters are a collation of basic quantitative data from workshops:

- Participants
- Profiles missing
- Session structure
- Follow-up method

In a late stage, this data was merged with the extended framework described in part 3, and shared with the Demo Duos for their validation and last update.

2.2 Observations

From the Control Parameters several observations are worth sharing. Overall, attendance numbers rose steadily and ended up above the 15 recommended Key Stakeholders per session, from slightly over 10 mid-project. Another interesting finding common to all demonstrators is that the sessions became shorter, often more dedicated to accommodate different expertise, cautious to not exhaust stakeholders as time went on. On the other hand, follow-up methods varied from one region to the other, with those more persistent benefiting in the long run from a more varied and numerous core group of attendees.

Some golden rules can thus be established: co-creation sessions should run for 4 hours in person or 2 online, with breaks to divide knowledge intensive parts from those more dynamic; the balance between manageable crowds, tools and representativeness remains somewhere around 10 and 20 stakeholders; and time and space should be provided for stakeholders to exchange before or after the session. No structure has proven more effective, with some demos opting for settings of morning only, others pushing into the afternoon, and even dividing in two days to maximise the outcome.

3.0 EXTENDED FRAMEWORK

Despite the more than satisfactory performance in engaging stakeholders, the Control Parameters alone were not enough to cover all the insights provided by demonstrators and stakeholders. Consequently, the Multi-Actor Approach methodology was reworked to include and link the perceived challenges. The preliminary findings were shared with the local partners in 1:1 meetings as the last consultations were taking place.

Assisted by FEUGA, the demo responsables validated these findings using a questionnaire based on the Control Parameters but also including inquiries about recommended practices (vertical and horizontal integration, facilitators, networks, 1:1 following, older case studies) and a reflection exercise [6] based on four principles: an agnostic stance, disorienting dilemmas, self-reflection, and non-iterative thinking.

The procedures designed at the start of the project have been expanded to reinforce previous research while providing more incentives to reporting and evaluation. This new systematic approach is designed to create reinforcing loops and solve the most persistent challenge: the ordeal of understanding what short-term added value is needed in each activity with stakeholders so that they are able to provide valuable insights and, in turn, set a baseline for capacity development that also appeals to the long-term conditions of the Innovation Ecosystem. The Best Practices certainly were of value to the local partners, but were not enough break this lock, lacking the necessary flexibility and continuity.

Figure 4. Systematic reporting as performed at the last stage of the project.

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This renewed approach to the stakeholder engagement evaluation provided several additional findings. There was room to improvement in knowledge integration despite the demos increasing collaboration and performance over time. The perceived risks and uncertainties remained high and limited the ability to react and create new avenues for the solution design and implementation. The Matrix, although useful in the initial phase, did not keep up and the Consultations proved the need to follow not only the profiles, but the coalitions that emerge from the interaction of stakeholders, and the solutions that they would like to pursue outside the consensus of the Innovation Ecosystem.

3.1 A radical theory of co-creation

TransformAr addressed the goal of Transformational Adaptation [7] in the parameters of Horizon 2020 and the Mission Adaptation Charter [8]. The strategy of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis defined and implemented in Work Package 3 reconciled the need for Transformative Adaptation with the selection of Pathways towards regional portfolios of solution, creating conditions for this via the Innovation Ecosystems. In contrast to the Ownership of Solutions defined in D5.6, the Solution Evaluation was not integrated in the Multi-Actor Approach. These factors need to influence the review of stakeholder engagement performance but also inform upcoming initiatives.

Figure 5. Multi-Actor Approach levels. © 2025 by FEUGA is licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

The combination of Adaptation Pathways with a bottom-up Multi-Actor Approach governance has demonstrated valid. The division of Technical and Geographical Dimensions stroke the desired balance

but there was little margin for reaction based on stakeholder feedback when the prioritised solutions faced bottlenecks. The Matrix did not account for involvement [9] as the project went on.

A basic requirement for Multi-Actor Approach governance is thus to provide a decision-support system as well. It can be based on a Capacity Needs Assessment unlocked by the agnostic Systemic Review and a Matrix based on solutions instead. These elements will have a greater chance of creating viable solutions while restoring the artificial conditions imposed during the co-creation process.

If feasible in the context of a given project, a forum-based approach can be followed for greater impact in the long-term and continuity, incentives for risk-taking and sustained commitment from stakeholders. This is an intuitive solution to reinforce feedback loops and repurposing already existing structures for knowledge exchange and policy making. It is advised that this governance model also includes ways to mix every participant intentional and regularly, for role switching can lead to alternative coalitions and is also a sign of the health of an Innovation Ecosystem.

The role of the Broker can also be redefined according to the level of Multi-Actor Approach desired. In order to assist in the agnostic self-reflection and evaluation, this figure should have a more critical judgement, actively reporting and validating the findings throughout the project, and specially for the charting and navigating of the methodologies available for stakeholder engagement. In this sense, a map can be defined to create clusters of practices that reinforce each other and answer to any desired outcome, expanding and leveraging on the capacities of the stakeholders to provide increasingly valuable insights for the viability of the solution and the continuity of the Innovation Ecosystem.

A MENU OF METHODOLOGIES

Figure 6. Example of a menu of methodologies to navigate stakeholder engagement. © 2025 by FEUGA is licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

3.2 Recommended practices

The TransformAr local partners have also validated a list of recommended practices that can improve the governance of the Innovation Ecosystems and how knowledge is shared and integrated. This list can serve as an expanded mindset from what EIP-AGRI set in 2017.

- › Emphasise short-term value
- › Avoid knowledge extractivism
- › Increase transparency
- › Share decision-making
- › Revive tacit knowledge
- › Foster role switching
- › Specialise and integrate
- › Remain responsive
- › Fight innovation inertia
- › Create mini-coalitions
- › Map involvement and solutions
- › Follow up with 1:1 meetings

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Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

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